

Farm diversification and the role of digital technologies: Evidence from the Farmer Intentions Survey 2023

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Summary

Purpose:

This briefing note examines current patterns and future intentions around farm diversification in Scotland, with a particular focus on the role of digital technologies. Drawing on the Farmer Intentions Survey (FIS) 2023, it explores which farmers are diversifying, the forms these activities take, and the barriers faced by those who have not diversified. The analysis considers demographic and farm-level characteristics as well as regional differences, and pays special attention to how connectivity, social media, and online platforms shape diversification opportunities, with implications for rural development and digital inclusion.

Key findings:

- While the majority of farmers do not intend to make any changes to the level of diversification activity on their farm, around a third intend to increase their diversification in the next five years.
- Amongst farms reporting diversification activities, renewable energy production and agri-tourism (mainly providing accommodation) dominate. Looking at the factors that differentiate diversified and non-diversified farms, we found few clear patterns that explain adoption.
- Farmers educated to university level are more likely to diversify – this is the case for renewable energy, agri-tourism and ‘other’ diversification categories.
- Tenure influences likelihood of producing renewable energy and ‘other’ diversification activities (in which forestry dominated), with tenant farmers less likely to diversify.
- We found no significant differences in likelihood of diversification according to farmers’ age or marital status. Likewise, we found no significant relationship between either farm size or farm type (livestock/arable/mixed).
- Amongst farmers who have not diversified, the primary perceived barriers relate to lack of resources and time. Lack of advice or information was not commonly perceived to be a major barrier to diversification.
- Social media and digital selling platforms support diversified businesses, however access to reliable and fast internet connections remains a major constraint upon farm diversification and rural innovation.

1. Introduction

Farm diversification has emerged as a critical strategy for rural sustainability, representing a strategic shift away from traditional core farming activities. Farmers are increasingly creating new goods or services by creatively utilizing their existing resources, offering opportunities for economic growth and managing financial risks through multiple revenue streams (Hansson et al., 2013).

While farm diversification can take many forms, moving into renewable energy production and agri-tourism represent the most common diversification approaches and this is where attention has been focused in the academic literature. Renewable energy production includes biomass, geothermal, wind, hydroelectric and solar energy, with wind and solar energy technologies particularly attractive due to their scalability and compatibility with existing farm infrastructure (Talbot, 2013; Jack et al., 2021). In the tourism and hospitality sector, diversification options include farm accommodation, amenities, leisure activities, events, attractions and farm shops (Talbot, 2013; Jack et al., 2021).

Digital connectivity in rural areas has previously been identified as a challenge for the farming sector. Existing inequalities in digital infrastructure provision are recognised in Scottish policies including the national digital strategy *A Changing Nation: How Scotland will Thrive in a Digital World*, and in the Reaching 100% (R100) programme which aims to extend superfast access to all homes and businesses in Scotland. Rural digital transformation offers considerable opportunities for farming households to diversify and generate additional income, however there is currently a lack of evidence on how digital technologies are used as part of farm diversification activities in the Scottish context.

Against this background, this policy brief presents analysis of questions on diversification from the Farmer Intentions Survey (FIS) 2023, a large-scale repeated cross-sectional survey of Scottish farmers, smallholders and crofters. The purpose of the analysis is to characterise the current state of play in relation to diversification on Scottish farms and assess the role of digital technologies - including digital connectivity, social media and online platforms - in supporting diversified farm businesses.

Specifically, we address the following **research questions**:

- 1) What can the FIS tell us about trends in farmer intentions around diversification over time?
- 2) How common are different forms of diversification activities in Scottish farms and what factors predict their adoption?
- 3) What barriers to diversification are experienced by farmers?
- 4) What role are digital technologies playing in farm diversification activities?

Information about the Farmer Intentions Survey 2023 methodology and the statistical approaches underpinning the findings presented in this brief are included in Appendix A.

2. Key findings

Trends in farmer intentions around diversification

We asked all respondents about changes in the level of diversification on their farm, croft, or smallholding over the past five years and their intentions for the next five years (Figure 1). While most respondents (65.1%) reported no change over the past five years, 18.7% said their diversification had increased. Looking ahead to the next five years, the majority (57.0%) do not intend to alter their current level of diversification, however almost a third (30.6%) intend to increase diversification activity. This is a similar proportion to those reporting intentions to increase diversification in the FIS 2018 wave (Kuhfuss et al., 2024).

Figure 1: Reported changes in the level of diversification in addition to agricultural production (e.g. agritourism, farm shop) in the past 5 years (n=1034) and intended changes in the next 5 years (n=1037). Error bars show $\pm 2SE$.

Adoption of different types of diversification activity

One quarter (n=484) of the FIS 2023 sample were selected to receive the module asking about diversification activities (Figure 2). Just over one third (34.1%) of those questioned reported that they operated diversification enterprises such as agri-tourism or renewable energy production on their farm. For these respondents, the most common diversification activity related to renewable energy generation, with 52.1% reporting that they produce renewable energy themselves only, a further 10.9% reporting that they both produce renewable energy themselves and rent land to others for this purpose, and 0.6% reporting that they do not produce themselves but do rent land to others to produce renewable energy. Of those reporting diversification activities, 43.0% operate agri-tourism on the farm. The most common type of agri-tourism reported was accommodation (80.3% of those operating an agri-tourism enterprise), followed by farm attractions (18.3%), cafes (8.5%), and food/drinks outlets (7.0%).

Figure 2: Distribution of responses to questions around diversification enterprises operated.

Factors predicting adoption of diversification activities

Logistic regression models were used to explore factors (demographic, farm-level and geographic) that predict adoption of different types of diversification activity – renewable energy production, agri-tourism, and other diversification enterprises e.g. forestry. The model results (reported in Appendix B) indicate very few statistically significant relationships between demographic, farm-level and geographic variables and the likelihood of reporting adoption of diversification activities.

Across all three types of diversification activity, a higher **level of educational award** was a significant predictor of adoption, with those educated to university level more likely to report adoption of renewable energy production, agri-tourism and other diversification activities than respondents whose highest level of education was school-level. Other demographic variables (gender, age) were not associated with adoption of diversification activities.

Farm size - whether small ($SLR < 0.5$), medium ($0.5 \leq SLR \leq 3$) or large farm ($SLR > 3$) - and farm type (whether livestock, arable, mixed other) were not associated with adoption of any of the three diversification activity types. Farm **tenure**, however, was a significant predictor of renewable energy production and operation of an ‘other’ diversification enterprise. Those who rented their farm were significantly less likely to report having adopted these types of diversification activities than owner-occupiers. However, there was no significant difference between those who rent some and own some of the land they farm compared to those who fully own the land.

Differences across **region** were observed mainly in relation to agri-tourism adoption, with farms in the Western Isles (Eilean an Iar), Highlands, and Scottish Borders most likely to report operating this form of diversification enterprise. Farmers on Orkney were most likely to report producing renewable energy, however overall there were few significant regional differences observed for renewable energy production and none in relation to ‘other’ diversification

enterprises. At the same time, it should be noted that this analysis is limited by subgroup sample size and the detection of significant differences is dependent on the region selected as a reference group against which other regions are compared.

Occupier working pattern and marital status were also explored as potential influencing factors. **Working patterns** were related only to diversification in the form of renewable energy production, with farmers who reported working only part-time on the farm, or not on the farm at all, less likely to be producing renewable energy. It is not clear why this might be. Farmers who recorded that they had a spouse were no more or less likely to report any of the three diversification types explored.

Barriers to diversification experienced by farmers

Those farmers who reported that they did not operate any diversification enterprises on the farm (n=319) were asked to indicate their level of agreement/disagreement with statements that might explain reasons for not diversifying (Figure 3). The responses indicate that the greatest perceived barriers to diversification relate to **resources** and **time**. More than half (54.2%) reported that they do not have the resources to set up other activities. While the survey question did not specify types of resources, this might include physical assets, labour and skills, supply chains etc. Almost half (48.6%) state that they do not have time to diversify. Additionally, 37.1% reported a lack of **access to finance** as a barrier.

Whilst these practical barriers dominated, a significant proportion do not see any need or value for their business in diversifying. Over one third report that there is no financial need for them to do so (34.8%) and a similar proportion are simply not interested in diversifying (34.0%), with almost as many again reporting scepticism around the potential profitability of new activities (30.6%). Around one quarter agreed that they lack access to advice or information on diversification (24.4%), whilst the majority (53.9%) disagreed. This suggests that while some farmers may benefit from advice, interventions to support farmers who are keen to diversify should focus not only on providing/signposting more information but also on addressing practical and financial barriers.

Figure 3: Barriers to diversification for respondents who do not operate diversification enterprises on their farm (n=319).

What role do digital technologies play in farm diversification?

Respondents were asked specifically about the influence of digital connectivity on diversification. Just over half of respondents (52.4%) reported that they have access to a reliable internet connection, and low internet speeds are a challenge for many, with around half (49.5%) of respondents agreeing or strongly agreeing with the statement ‘low internet speed has been a problem for diversifying’ (Figure 4).

Figure 4: Agreement with statements on internet speed and reliability (n=484).

Respondents who reported operating a diversification enterprise on their farm (n=165) were asked about whether they use social media and online selling platforms for their diversification activity (Figure 5). A sizeable minority (43.6%) reported use of social media for this purpose. Amongst these respondents (n=72), the most used platform was Facebook, followed by Instagram. Much fewer used Twitter (now X) or Tiktok, but 17% reporting using other social media platforms. This included mentions of Whatsapp, YouTube, and some web resources or platforms that may not be considered social media (e.g. own business website).

Figure 5: Use of digital platforms in diversification activities.

Slightly over a third (34.5%) of those operating diversification enterprises reported using online selling platforms. Respondents mentioned a range of specific platforms, most of which relate to the marketing and booking of tourist accommodation. Of these the most frequently mentioned were Airbnb, Visit Scotland, and Booking.com. Several respondents also mentioned having their own website. Very few respondents mentioned other platforms not associated with letting accommodation.

We also explored the perceptions of those managing diversified farms (n=165) regarding the impact of the UK's exit from the EU and the COVID-19 pandemic on their diversification activity. The majority (70.3%) felt that economic opportunities for diversification remained unchanged since Brexit, with few (6.7%) reporting an increase in opportunities and more (23.0%) reporting a decrease. Respondents had mixed views on the extent to which COVID-19 provided an opportunity to explore digital options for selling and marketing, with 32.1% agreeing that it provided an opportunity and 28.5% disagreeing, with 39.4% neither agreeing nor disagreeing.

3. Discussion and conclusions

Analysis of farmers' intentions shows most do not plan to change their level of diversification, though about a third aim to increase it in the next five years. Despite similar intentions in 2018, fewer than one-fifth actually diversified by 2023. While COVID-19 and Brexit may have disrupted plans, the pandemic also created opportunities through digital selling and marketing, as demonstrated by research in the Highlands on how digital tools supported social capital and access to alternative markets (Noble et al., 2023).

Among diversified farms, renewable energy and agri-tourism dominate. Education was the strongest predictor of diversification, consistent with earlier studies (Morris & Bowen, 2020), while age showed no effect, contrary to expectations (Ge et al., 2017; Sutherland et al., 2016). This may reflect sample limits or suggest a need to untangle education and generational factors. Prior research highlights the role of household skills and interests and motivations to create opportunities for multiple family members (Hansson et al., 2013), however we found no difference between married and unmarried respondents in adoption of diversification activity.

Farm characteristics also played a role: tenure predicted renewable energy and forestry-related diversification, but farm size did not affect adoption or intentions. Regional variation was most evident in agri-tourism, aligning with earlier findings of activity concentrated in scenic areas and near population centres (Hopkins et al., undated).

For occupiers of non-diversified farms, the most common barriers to diversification reported related to lack of resources, time and financing. High initial investment costs and the associated financial risks of expansion, along with concerns about long-term investment viability often underpin reluctance (Morris & Bowen, 2020). Human resource limitations are also recognised to impact significantly on diversification potential. Beyond having the resources required to operate a diversification enterprise, success is also tied to market awareness and previous business experience (Talbot, 2013). However, lack of advice or information was not perceived to be a major barrier to diversification amongst farmers in the FIS.

Finally, the analysis highlighted the prominence and diversity of digital platforms used in marketing and selling the products and services of diversification enterprises. Almost half of diversified farms use social media (most commonly Facebook) and over one third use online selling platforms, particularly for tourist accommodation booking. This supports recent research pointing to the importance of 'lower tech' solutions like social media for smaller farms e.g. for reaching new markets (Salemink et al., 2025; Noble et al., 2024). At the same time, however, lack of access to reliable and fast internet connection remains a major challenge for diversifying. Whilst the proportion reporting that internet speed hinders diversification reduced from 58% in

the FIS 2018 to 50% in 2023, this underscores the importance of current efforts to improve superfast broadband coverage and reduce inequalities in digital access between urban and rural areas for rural innovation and economic development.

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Acknowledgements

This work was funded by the Rural & Environment Science & Analytical Services Division of the Scottish Government, as part of the Strategic Research Programme 2022-2027 (JHI-B3-1 - Co-designing and implementing best-fit farming practices ('COMBINE') and SRUC-B3-1 - Ensuring positive behavioural change for farmers towards best practice for clean growth: economic and behavioural investigations). The authors would like to thank Leanne Townsend, Sharon Flanigan, Christina Noble and Rachel Creaney for inputs to questionnaire design and early discussions on the academic literature. The interpretations expressed in this report are the authors' own and do not necessarily reflect those of the Scottish Government or RESAS.

Appendix A: Methodology

Data

The Farmers Intention Survey (FIS) is a large-scale telephone-based survey of Scottish farmers, crofters and smallholders. It has been run by The James Hutton Institute and Scotland's Rural College (SRUC) every five years since 2013. The objective of the FIS is to gain a better understanding of farmers management decisions both in the past, and their intentions for the future. This policy brief reports the findings from the 3rd wave of the FIS conducted in 2023. With the aim to have a representative sample of Scottish farms and agriculture, we contacted 13,652 Scottish farm holdings by post and asked them to take part in the survey. The list of farmers was provided by Scottish Government's June 2021 Agricultural Census (JAC) team. Overall, we received 2,029 responses from farmers, crofters and smallholders who took part. The FIS 2023 data was merged with data from with data from the June Agricultural Census (2021) and Rural Payments Inspection Department (RPID) data (for the year 2022).

The questionnaire contained a set of 'core modules' are asked of all respondents in each wave, along with a set of wave-specific topic modules. The analysis in this brief focuses on core module questions about diversification (section 3.1) and questions drawn from the FIS 2023 diversification topic module, which was asked of one-quarter of the sample (selected randomly) (section 3.2-3.4).

Analysis

Chi-square (χ^2) tests were used to test whether responses differed between groups. Statistically significant results ($p \leq 0.05$) indicate that there is a significant association with the factor that respondents were grouped on.

Binary logistic regression (logit) models were used to analyse the extent to which the different predicted uptake of different types of diversification activity. This approach allowed us to statistically isolate the effect of each predictor variable, while controlling for effects of the others included in the models. From this analysis we are able to identify what factors are associated with a higher or lower likelihood of uptake of diversification activities.

Appendix B: Model results

Table B1: Results of logistic regression models predicting uptake of agritourism options of producing renewable energy, operating an agri-tourism enterprise, and other forms of diversification including forestry. Odds ratios >1 indicate greater odds of uptake, compared to the reference category. Odds ratios <1 indicate lower odds compared to the reference category.

	Renewable energy production	Agri-tourism	Other diversification enterprise
	Odds ratio	Odds ratio	Odds ratio
Age (Ref=75 and over)			
35 and under	.175	.193	.181
36-40	.346	1.150	.569
41-44	.671	.919	.000
45-54	.976	1.372	.576
55-64	1.348	1.635	.894
65-74	.710	.658	.601
Gender (Ref=Male)			
Female	.695	.928	.487
Education (Ref=School)			
College	1.666	.975	2.910*
University	2.996**	2.543*	8.538**
Farm size (Ref= Large [SLR > 3])			
Small (SLR <0.5)	.435	.392	.585
Med (0.5 ≤ SLR ≤ 3)	.875	.715	.853
Farm type (Ref=livestock)			
Arable	1.505	.479	1.298
Mixed	1.439	1.504	.902
Other	.837	1.156	1.294
Tenure (Ref=owned)			
Rented	.400*	.903	.240*
Mixed	1.794	1.142	.847
Occupier marital status (Ref=unmarried)			
	1.677	.899	1.441
Occupier working pattern (Ref= full time on the farm)			
Part-time (half-time or more)	.400*	.633	.821
Part time (less than half-time)	.437*	.858	.730
Does not work on farm	.084*	.714	.424
Region (Ref= NE Scotland¹)			
Argyll & Bute	.831	4.717*	2.847
Ayrshire	.401	4.035	3.972
Clyde Valley	1.149	5.818*	4.181
Dumfries and Galloway	1.607	2.069	.854
East Central	1.664	3.755	1.951
Eileanan an Iar	2.136	14.584*	.000
Fife	1.375	3.799	2.679
Highland	.921	6.533**	3.234
Lothian	1.454	.000	1.673
Orkney	3.349*	2.416	.877
Scottish Borders	1.658	6.052**	3.447
Shetland	.799	1.571	1.686
Tayside	.797	3.821	2.129
N	457	457	457
Nagelkerke R ²	.222	.182	.245

(*) Significant at $p \leq 0.05$; (**) = Significant at $p \leq 0.01$

¹ NE Scotland was selected as the reference category because it was, along with Highland, the region with highest representation (n=87) among the respondents who were asked questions on diversification.